

PRIORITY RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIABETES MELLITUS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: A CLINICAL ASSESSMENT

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Introduction. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on global health, contributing to a surge in the incidence of non-communicable diseases, particularly diabetes mellitus (DM). SARS-CoV-2, the virus responsible for COVID-19, has been implicated in damaging pancreatic beta cells, which may lead to impaired insulin production and the onset of type 2 diabetes, especially in individuals recovering from severe COVID-19. A growing number of post-COVID-19 cases have shown newly diagnosed diabetes, raising concerns about the virus's role in the development of metabolic disorders.

The pandemic has also strained healthcare systems, disrupting routine care for patients with pre-existing diabetes, leading to disease progression and decompensation. Diabetic patients who contracted COVID-19 often experienced more severe disease symptoms, more frequent episodes of hyperglycemia, and complications like diabetic ketoacidosis. Unvaccinated individuals demonstrated a higher likelihood of experiencing severe symptoms and prolonged metabolic instability in the post-COVID-19 period compared to their vaccinated counterparts.

Vaccination against COVID-19 has shown benefits not only in reducing the severity of the viral infection but also in stabilizing glycemic control and lowering the risk of diabetes-related complications. This research aims to identify key risk factors contributing to diabetes onset during the pandemic, with an emphasis on the role of COVID-19 infection and the protective effects of vaccination in mitigating metabolic disruptions.

Objective. The main objective of this study is to identify and evaluate the key risk factors leading to the development and progression of diabetes mellitus during the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly focusing on the impact of SARS-CoV-2 infection and the potential protective role of vaccination in mitigating disease severity and metabolic dysregulation.

Materials and Methods. This clinical study was conducted from 2022 to 2023 at the Khatyrchinsky Medical District Association's endocrinology department. The study included 242 patients selected using a prospective cohort design. The cohort consisted of 138 men and 104 women, with an average age of 64.3 ± 2.7 years. Patients were classified into three groups based on vaccination status and the timing of diabetes onset: Group 1: 102 unvaccinated patients who developed type 2 diabetes after contracting COVID-19. Group 2: 53 vaccinated patients who developed type 2 diabetes after recovering from COVID-19. Group 3: 87 patients with pre-existing type 2 diabetes before contracting COVID-19.

Comprehensive clinical evaluations were conducted for all patients, which included detailed medical histories, monitoring of blood pressure, BMI, and laboratory tests (complete blood counts, biochemical tests, and coagulograms). Instrumental diagnostics, such as X-rays, ultrasounds, and electrocardiograms (ECG), were performed to assess cardiovascular and renal function. Glycemic control was evaluated through fasting blood glucose levels, HbA1c, and insulin sensitivity. Additionally, complications like diabetic neuropathy, retinopathy, and ketoacidosis episodes were monitored. The study aimed to assess the relationship between COVID-19 infection, vaccination status, and diabetes progression.

Results. The study revealed significant differences in the severity of symptoms and complications among the three patient groups. Unvaccinated patients in Group 1 displayed more severe diabetic symptoms, including chronic fatigue, polydipsia, polyuria, frequent hyperglycemia, and episodes of decompensation. Complications such as neuropathy and retinopathy were more common, with these patients requiring more frequent hospitalizations. Nearly 90% reported pronounced weakness, and 85% experienced severe fatigue. These patients also had unstable blood glucose levels, leading to frequent hyperglycemic and hypoglycemic episodes.

On the other hand, vaccinated patients in Group 2 showed milder symptoms and fewer complications. Although hyperglycemia was still present, it was less severe, and symptoms like weight loss and dry mouth were less frequent. This group also exhibited more stable blood glucose levels with fewer episodes of decompensation. Furthermore, fewer patients (25%) reported chronic fatigue compared to the unvaccinated group (50%), and complications like neuropathy and retinopathy were less prevalent.

Patients in Group 3, who had pre-existing diabetes, experienced worsening conditions after contracting COVID-19, especially if they were unvaccinated. They faced more frequent hyperglycemic episodes, severe fatigue, and exacerbated diabetic complications. About 80% reported weakness, and 40% experienced chronic fatigue. The progression of diabetes-related complications, such as neuropathy and retinopathy, was more pronounced in this group.

Conclusion. This study underscores the fact that unvaccinated diabetic patients who contracted COVID-19 experienced more severe symptoms and a higher incidence of complications compared to vaccinated individuals. Vaccination was associated with reduced inflammation, improved metabolic control, and fewer diabetes-related complications. These findings highlight the critical role of vaccination in managing diabetes during pandemics, not only in preventing severe COVID-19 but also in stabilizing metabolic control and reducing the long-term risk of complications. Effective diabetes management in post-COVID-19 patients should include vaccination, lifestyle modifications, and continuous monitoring to prevent complications and enhance health outcomes.

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